

Relative length, arm ratio, and classification of the chromosomes of *Oryza meyeriana*.

Chromosome number	Relative length (%)	Arm ratio (short/long)	Classification ^a
1	11.80	0.82	M
2	11.48	0.90	M
3	9.87	0.67	SM
4	8.80	0.70	SM
5	8.69	0.73	SM
6	8.31	0.69	SM
7	8.11	0.73	SM
8	7.26	0.63	SM
9	6.97	0.93	M
10	6.79	0.88	M
11	6.17	0.69	SM
12	5.74 ^b	0.37	SAT

^aM = metacentric, SM = submetacentric, SAT = satellite. Arm ratio: M = (1.0–0.76), SM = (0.75–0.25). ^bThe length of the satellite is not included in the length of the chromosome.

A study of Neolithic carbonized rice grains excavated from Hemudu, China

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Rice grains excavated from Hemudu, China (6950±130 BC) are known to be some of the world's oldest remains of rice cultivation. We studied the variation in

these grains to improve our understanding of the origin and domestication of cultivated rice in China.

The length and width of 105 of the grains were measured using an enlarged photograph. About half of the grains were awnless. The grain length ranged from 5.2 to 8.6 mm, with an average of 7.1 mm, and the grain width ranged from 2.1 to 3.2 mm, with an average of 2.8 mm. The grain length-width ratio (L:W) was 1.7-3.2, with an average of 2.6. These findings suggest

that the Hemudu rice population had large variation in grain shape and awn characteristics.

Our earlier study found a few wild rice grains (*O. rufipogon*) among the rice grains excavated at Hemudu.

We therefore infer that about 7,000 yr ago, people in Hemudu did primitive rice cultivation, and that the middle and lower basin of Yangtze River is a homeland of cultivated rice in China. ■

Length, width, and shape distribution of 105 rice grains excavated from Hemudu, China.

Grain trait	Distribution														
Length (mm)	<5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	6.5	6.8	7.9	7.4	7.7	8.0	8.3	8.6			
(no.)	1	2	3	6	7	21	29	11	9	11	4	1			
(%)	0.9	1.9	2.9	5.7	6.7	20.0	27.6	10.5	8.6	10.5	3.8	0.9			
Width (mm)	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.2			
(no.)	2	3	3	1	5	9	20	24	18	15	4	1			
(%)	1.9	2.9	2.9	0.9	4.8	8.6	19.0	22.9	17.1	14.3	3.8	0.9			
L-W ratio	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	>3.1
(no.)	1	0	1	2	5	7	5	12	12	16	13	5	16	4	6
(%)	0.9	0	0.9	1.9	4.8	6.6	4.8	11.4	11.4	15.2	12.4	4.8	15.2	3.8	5.7

Classification of A genome species in the genus *Oryza* using nuclear DNA markers

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We did a new analysis of the restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLPs) of 67 accessions of A genome species in the

genus *Oryza*, which contains *O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. barthii*, *O. longistaminata*, *O. glumaepatula*, and *O. meridionalis*, and of the materials previously analyzed by Nakano et al (1992) (see figure). A total of 192 accessions of the A genome species were analyzed.

RFLPs were detected for combinations of *Dra*I-digested total DNA and 21 single copy genomic clones. Genetic distances between accessions were quantified as

$$D = -\ln [2M_{xy}/(M_x+M_y)]$$

where M_x and M_y were the total fragments in accessions X and Y, respectively, and M_{xy} were the common fragments observed between accessions X and Y. A dendrogram was then constructed by the UPGMA method using 64 of the 67 new accessions and 12 previously analyzed accessions as a reference (see figure).

A genome species were classified into five major groups: Asian (*O. sativa*, *O. rufipogon*, and *O. nivara*), *O. glumaepatula*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. barthii*, *O. longistaminata*, and *O. meridionalis*. *O. glumaepatula* had

IRRN reminder

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

RFLP-derived dendrogram of 76 accessions. Sixty-four out of 67 accessions provided by IRRI, and 12 previously analyzed accessions of *O. sativa*, *O. rufipogon*, and *O. glaberrima* (Nakano et al 1992), were included for reference; three *O. rufipogon* accessions from Papua New Guinea were excluded.

closer affinity to the *O. glaberrima-O. barthii* group than to the Asian *O. rufipogon* group, although it had been considered a subtype of *O. rufipogon*.

The Asian group comprised four or five loosely knit groups, each corresponding to the indica type (including some *O. rufipogon*), japonica type (including *O. rufipogon* from China), *O. rufipogon* (consisting of several subgroups), and *O. nivara* (see figure). Some *O. rufipogon-O. nivara* showed close affinity to cultivated rice, as suggested by previous studies (Wang et al 1992, Nakano et al 1992).

Three accessions of perennial *O. rufipogon* from Papua New Guinea (excluded from the figure) carried both fragments of *O. rufipogon* and *O. meridionalis*. Although no *O. meridionalis* has been reported from Papua New Guinea so far, it is possible that some exist in the country and that the natural hybrids between *O. rufipogon* and *O. meridionalis* could have survived until now.

The classification among species matched well with the findings of previous studies (Morishima 1969, Second 1985, Wang et al 1992). Further analysis is needed to reveal the relationships among Asian subgroups.

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Detection of D genome chromosomes by genomic in situ hybridization

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Based on chromosome pairing at meiosis, it is known that the genus *Oryza* has five genomes (A, B, C, E, and F) in the diploid species. Tetraploid species with BC or CD genomes have also been found, although a diploid species with the D genome has not yet been discovered. The D genome is only found in tetraploids (*O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, and *O. latifolia* from Central and South America) in combination with the C genome.

In this study, we visualized D genome chromosomes on a glass slide in a CD genome tetraploid species. We used a chromosome painting method in which we applied the genomic in situ hybridization (GISH) method, using the total genomic DNA isolated from a C genome diploid species, *O. officinalis* (2n=24), labeled with biotin as the probe. *O. latifolia* was used to prepare chromosomes.

Chromosome samples were prepared by an enzymatic macerated/air drying method. The chromosome samples were treated with an enzymatic mixture (2% cellulase onozuka RS, 1.5% macerozyme R-200, 0.3% Pectolyase Y-23), proteinase K (1 mg ml⁻¹), 4.5% acetic acid, and RNase A (1 mg ml⁻¹) prior to in situ hybridization to get clear genome-specific fluorescent signals on small chromosomes.

The post-treatment removed cytoplasmic debris, cellular protein, and RNAs that cause nonspecific signals. In addition, a modified thermal cycler with a flat aluminum plate was developed and used to precisely control temperature. The results of GISH were analyzed using CHIAS 2, an image-analyzing system that provides clear fluorescent signal reproduction. This system can capture the fluorescent signals of GISH within a second, enhance weak signals, and even superimpose the signal images onto the original chromosome

We identified 24 C genome chromosomes, detected by the fluorescent probe of *O. officinalis*, from a mixture of 48 *O. latifolia* chromosomes belonging to the C and D genomes. All 24 D genome chromosomes were clearly identified using the imaging method, as were 24 C genome chromosomes from the 48 chromosomes with B and C genomes.

We also found differences in the relative strength of fluorescent signals between C and D genomes, and between B and C genomes. The differences in the fluorescent signal strength between B and C genome chromosomes were more distinct than those between C and D genome chromosomes, despite applying the same probe. These differences reflect the sequence homology between the C and D or B genomes. The D genome is considered to be more similar to the C genome than to the B genome.

We will continue to use the GISH method to provide new information about the relationships among the six genomes in *Oryza*. ■

Fingerprinting rice germplasm using ALP and PCR-based RFLP

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Morphological and isozyme markers provide a simple method for classifying rice collections. However, the markers available and their level of polymorphism are inconveniently low. DNA markers, on the

other hand, are abundant, high in their level of polymorphism, and known to be useful for germplasm surveys.

We evaluated the usefulness of converting mapped restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers to polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based markers, such as amplicon length polymorphism (ALP), and PCR-based RFLP (Ghareyazie et al 1995). This is the first report on applying ALP and or PCR to classify rice and on classifying Iranian rice varieties at the DNA level.